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- 13.00.02 Ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi (sohalar bo'yicha)
- 13.00.03 Maxsus pedagogika
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- 13.00.05 Kasb-hunar ta'limi nazariyasi va metodikasi
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- 13.00.08 Maktabgacha ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi
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- 03.00.00 Biologiya fanlari
- 09.00.00 Falsafa fanlari
- 10.00.00 Filologiya fanlari
- 11.00.00 Geografiya fanlari

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COMPUTER-BASED FORMATIVE ASSESSMENT: ADVANTAGES AND CHALLENGES IN TEACHING ENGLISH TO HIGH SCHOOL STUDENTS

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Abstract: This article aims to investigate the pros and cons of the practical application of Computer-Aided Tools (CAT) in formative assessment for high school students. The study is based on a review of available studies, journal articles, and websites relevant to the concept. The results of the research provide evidence of several advantages, including active participation, instantaneous progress monitoring, and the simplification of processes involved in student progression tracking. CAT in this paper emphasizes the applicability of Computer-Aided Formative Assessment (CAFA) tools in learning. CAFA also highlights the most crucial drawbacks, among which are limited access, technological effects, and the lack of direct contact between teachers and students. The authors of the study note that the integration of technological tools should ideally be complemented with personal teacher feedback. Practical implications involve intensive training for teachers as well as the enhancement of relevant structures and regulations addressing data safety and fairness. It is suggested that computer-assisted tools may enhance best practices in language education within the EFL environment.

Key words: Computer-Aided Assessment, Computer-Aided Tools, Formative Assessment, Online Assessment, Formative Feedback, Computer-Based Testing.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqola o'rta maktab o'quvchilarini formatif baholash jarayonida kompyuter yordamida yaratilgan vositalardan (CAT) foydalanishning afzallik va kamchiliklarini o'rganishga qaratilgan. Tadqiqot mavjud ilmiy maqolalar, tadqiqotlar va mazkur tushunchaga oid veb-saytlarni tahlil qilish asosida olib borildi. Natijalar faol ishtirok, darhol monitoring qilish imkoniyati va o'quvchilar rivojlanishini kuzatish jarayonlarining soddalashtirilishi kabi bir qator afzalliklarni ko'rsatadi. Ushbu maqolada CAT kompyuter yordamidagi formatif baholash (CAFA) vositalarining o'quv jarayonida qo'llanishini ta'kidlaydi. Shu bilan birga, CAFA vositalarining eng muhim kamchiliklari ham ajratib ko'rsatilgan: cheklangan imkoniyatlar, texnologiyaning ta'siri va o'qituvchi hamda o'quvchi o'rtasidagi bevosita aloqa yetishmasligi. Mualliflarning ta'kidlashicha, texnologik vositalarni qo'llash shaxsiy o'qituvchi fikr-mulohazalari bilan to'ldirilishi lozim. Amaliy natijalar sifatida o'qituvchilar uchun maxsus tayyorgarlikni kuchaytirish, shuningdek, ma'lumotlar xavfsizligi va adolatlilik masalalariga oid tegishli tartib-qoidalarni takomillashtirish zarurligi qayd etiladi. Kompyuter yordamidagi vositalar EFL (ingliz tili xorijiy til sifatida) muhitida til o'qitishning eng yaxshi amaliyotlarini yanada samarali qilishga yordam berishi mumkinligi taklif etiladi.

Kalit so'zlar: Kompyuter yordamidagi baholash, kompyuter yordamidagi vositalar, formatif baholash, onlayn baholash, formatif fikr-mulohaza, kompyuterga asoslangan test.

Аннотация: В данной статье рассматриваются преимущества и недостатки практического применения компьютерных инструментов (CAT) в формате формирующего оценивания учащихся средней школы. Исследование проведено на основе анализа доступных научных публикаций, статей и интернет-ресурсов, связанных с данной проблематикой. Результаты показывают ряд преимуществ, включая активное участие, мгновенный мониторинг прогресса и упрощение процессов отслеживания развития учащихся. В статье подчеркивается применимость инструментов компьютерного формирующего оценивания (CAFA) в образовательном процессе. Вместе с тем отмечены и основные недостатки: ограниченный доступ, влияние технологий и отсутствие прямого контакта между учителем и учеником. Авторы подчеркивают, что использование технологических средств должно сопровождаться личной обратной связью со стороны учителя. Практические рекомендации включают необходимость интенсивной подготовки педагогов, а также совершенствование соответствующих структур и регламентов по вопросам безопасности данных и справедливости. Предполагается, что компьютерные инструменты могут способствовать улучшению передовой практики в преподавании иностранных языков в среде EFL.

Ключевые слова: Компьютерное оценивание, компьютерные инструменты, формирующее оценивание, онлайн-оценивание, формирующая обратная связь, компьютерное тестирование.

INTRODUCTION

Assessment helps learners and teachers achieve learning goals. Formative Assessment (FA) is a process that evaluates learners' understanding while teaching a lesson. There are several types of assessment in education, namely Formative Assessment [1], Summative Assessment [2], Diagnostic Assessment [3], Peer Assessment [4], Self-Assessment [5], Ipsative Assessment [6], and others. FA is a process of evaluating students' understanding of the lesson during instruction. In addition, FA focuses on learners' needs and progress by providing feedback rather than grades, with the sole purpose of improving students' learning outcomes [7]. Although there are several types of assessments in education, FA is widely recognized as a crucial tool for evaluating learning comprehension, pupils' progress, and areas that require further improvement [8]. For students of EFL, particularly at the intermediate level, FA plays a significant role in identifying learners' needs, highlighting their strengths, and addressing aspects of a topic that need more attention. The rapid development of educational technology and the introduction of concepts such as Teachers' Technological, Pedagogical, and Content Knowledge (TPACK), along with the arrival of Learning Management Systems (LMSs), are widely discussed among academicians in terms of their advantages and disadvantages. Besides traditional assessment tools, Computer-Aided Assessment Tools (CAATs) such as Kahoot [9], Quizizz [10], Google Forms [11], Socrative [12], Edmodo [13], Blackboard [14], Formative [15], Microsoft Forms [16], Nearpod [17], Quizlet [18], and many others provide opportunities for immediate assessment, feedback, and learner motivation. Especially in university-level EFL teaching and learning settings, these online tools are now widely used [19].

LITERATURE REVIEW

Assessment is a critical aspect of every curriculum. It holds significant importance in education because it exerts a wide array of powerful impacts on what teachers and students do and how schools function [20]. Formative Assessment (FA) has been widely acknowledged as an effective way to improve language learning outcomes in EFL classroom environments. Formative assessments can visualize the distance between learners' current level and the desired lesson outcome by collecting productive feedback during interaction with students in the teaching process. Consequently, teachers can adjust their methods and techniques to better cover the lesson. Moreover, in EFL contexts, formative assessment fosters not only linguistic competencies but also builds learners' confidence and motivation [21]. The gaps identified in this paper are as follows. While there are studies conducted on the benefits of formative assessment, and these are undoubtedly well-documented, limited research is available on its integration with Computer-Aided Assessment Tools (CAAT). This paper seeks to address these gaps by exploring the advantages and challenges of CAAT in EFL settings.

The emergence of CAAT, as a consequence of integrating technology into formative assessment, has broadened its application. The use of tools like Kahoot and gamified formative assessments sustains student engagement through interactive quizzes that provide instant feedback. Digital formative assessments enhance learners' motivation, encourage active participation, and create a real-time evaluation atmosphere for learning outcomes. CAATs are designed to be user-friendly; hence, they make learning and assessment more engaging and contribute to continuous learning and improved performance [9]. Moreover, Sharma and Gao highlighted the distinctive features of CAAT, such as personalized experiences and collaborative functionalities, which make learning enjoyable while enabling educators to track progress and address individual learners' needs effectively [10]. Lye and Koh compared Google Forms and Kahoot, concluding that Google Forms function similarly to Kahoot [11, 12, 13, 14, 15, 16, 17, 18, 25].

Inappropriate learning methods hamper learner outcomes and interest [22]. The role of formative assessment is reflected in several educational theories. Vygotsky's (1978) Zone of Proximal Development (ZPD) theory emphasizes the importance of feedback in offering learners productive insight to reach higher levels of understanding. Similarly, the constructivist approach, rooted in Piaget's (1950) work, supports formative practices by advocating for active learner engagement and collaborative knowledge construction. These theories align with the principles of formative assessment, underlining its role in scaffolding learning and fostering continuous development.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

As this study aims to investigate the pros and cons of CAAT based on its formative nature, the researcher employs a qualitative research design, focusing on a comprehensive review and analysis of existing journals, newspaper articles, website sources, and related literature. The aim is to synthesize current findings on the advantages and disadvantages of using CAAT for formative assessments in EFL teaching and learning environments.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

This broader review of existing resources on CAAT for formative assessment has unveiled the following key findings in conjunction with EFL teaching and learning among intermediate-level high school students. Advantages of CAAT: CAATs enhance students' engagement and build motivation. Tools like Kahoot! and Quizizz almost always demonstrate their attractive nature by engaging students through gamification and interactive characteristics. Instantaneous feedback, competitive elements, and visual aids add a more dynamic learning environment ^[10]. Real-time feedback allows students to identify their strengths and weaknesses, leading to self-regulated learning skills ^[23]. Unlike traditional tests, CAATs simplify the process of test administration, grading, and the analysis and reporting of results ^[11]. Nowadays, with a single mouse click, results and reports on students' performance can be generated and are ready for either printing or sharing via email, Learning Management Systems, or messengers. This saves teachers' time spent on preparing test papers, proofreading, printing, safekeeping, marking, and preparing reports, as well as many other tasks. In addition, it reduces the cost of printing and related expenses.

Thanks to CAATs, teachers' workloads are reduced while more accurate reports of test records and essential results are maintained.

Synchronously or asynchronously connected tools make tests easily accessible, and test takers can complete them at their own pace. This flexible nature of CAATs allows learners to take tests multiple times and enables teachers to identify learners' knowledge gaps and address them effectively ^[24]. Gamified test systems like Kahoot! and Quizizz make assessments fun, reduce test anxiety, and increase students' interest in tests ^[10]. The use of visual and auditory items such as videos, sounds, and interactive media in CAATs further motivates learners to enjoy testing ^[27]. Promotion of peer interaction and collaborative learning are other vital attributes of CAATs, particularly through team-based quizzes and discussion prompts on several platforms like Kahoot!. Last but not least, these tools have already become part of the educational system and procedures, are undoubtedly unavoidable, and possess numerous benefits compared to previous eras.

Disadvantages of CAAT: Not everyone is skilled in digital media, and CAAT teachers may need special training to handle CAATs ^[11, 23]. Not all students and teachers have stable internet access or reliable digital devices, which creates an equity gap in learning opportunities ^[28]. Issues such as software glitches, connectivity shortages, and compatibility problems can disrupt the test-taking process and hamper learning progress ^[29]. Educators should also be cautious about overemphasizing gamification. While there is evidence that gamification can boost engagement, it may detract from deeper active learning, as pupils might focus more on earning points and badges instead of understanding lessons ^[10]. Reduced teacher-learner interaction in CAATs can limit the depth of personalized feedback teachers are able to provide ^[31]. Assessing learners with open-ended questions or complex tasks such as essay writing and spoken language proficiency remains a challenge for CAATs, which are better aligned with factual content and multiple-choice questions ^[24]. Increased dependence on infrastructure such as electricity and internet connectivity also impacts outcomes ^[29], often providing excuses for learners to avoid completing homework or tests on time. Some researchers suggest that CAATs may create opportunities for cheating ^[25] and reduce learners' creativity ^[27]. Furthermore, requiring students to create user accounts with personal information raises data privacy concerns and possible misuse of data ^[28].

CONCLUSION

The compulsory inclusion of computer-aided tools for formative assessment (CAFA) in an EFL teaching and learning environment offers numerous benefits. For instance, students receive real-time feedback, which increases their engagement in learning activities while also reducing the burden of data collection and management. These tools align with the current shift toward digitalization, where 21st-century skills are increasingly emphasized, and they are particularly beneficial for improving high school students' English proficiency.

However, challenges such as limited accessibility, technical difficulties, and reduced interaction between teachers and students necessitate the careful implementation of computer-aided assessment tools (CAATs) in EFL contexts. To maximize the benefits of CAFA, teachers should aim to integrate technological tools with personalized instructional responses. Additionally, educational institutions should address infrastructural barriers, provide comprehensive teacher training, and enforce effective educational policies that ensure data protection and equitable access to resources. For continued improvement in EFL settings, future research should focus on promoting the use of innovative assessment instruments that evaluate advanced levels of English proficiency, including critical thinking and creativity, thereby enhancing their overall utility. By leveraging the advantages of CAATs while mitigating their limitations, it is possible to significantly enrich the learning experiences of EFL students.

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- 13.00.00 Pedagogika fanlari
 - 13.00.01 Pedagogika nazariyasi. Pedagogik ta'limotlar tarixi
 - 13.00.02 Ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi (sohalar bo'yicha)
 - 13.00.03 Maxsus pedagogika
 - 13.00.04 Jismoniy tarbiya va sport mashg'ulotlari nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.05 Kasb-hunar ta'limi nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.06 Elektron ta'lim nazariyasi va metodikasi (ta'lim sohaları va bosqichlari bo'yicha)
 - 13.00.07 Ta'limda menejment
 - 13.00.08 Maktabgacha ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.09 Ijtimoiy pedagogika
 - 07.00.00 Tarix fanlari
 - 19.00.00 Psixologiya fanlari
 - 01.00.00 Fizika-matematika fanlari
 - 02.00.00 Kimyo fanlari
 - 03.00.00 Biologiya fanlari
 - 09.00.00 Falsafa fanlari
 - 10.00.00 Filologiya fanlari
 - 11.00.00 Geografiya fanlari

MAKTABGACHA VA MAKTAB TA'LIMI

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